

Additional File 8. Uncropped membranes Supplementary Figure S6

anti-Myc mouse monoclonal (1st antibody)
(Clone 4A6, EMD Millipore Corp, 1:1000)

anti-FLAG mouse monoclonal (1st antibody)
(Clone M2, Sigma, 1:1000)

anti-β-actin mouse monoclonal (2nd antibody)
(Clone C4, Santa Cruz, 1:10000)

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